

Volume 9, Number 2, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Geo studies is a peer-reviewed journal, published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. The purpose of the journal is to make quickly available the fruits of Geography related researches with emphasis on the tropical environment. Contributions are therefore invited from any part of the broad field constituted by geographical or spatial sciences and studies in their economic, political, social and policy dimensions. Research may be broadly defined, but must be sound in methodology, critical, entertaining, analytical, make contribution to existing knowledge and conclusions drawn must address contemporary issues.

CALL FOR PAPERS

We cordially request the submission of original papers for possible inclusion in the forthcoming issue of GEO-STUDIES FORUM (ISSN 1596-4116), published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin.

AREAS OF INTEREST

This scholarly peer-reviewed journal accepts original articles covering, but not limited to, the following areas:

- Geography
- Environmental Management
- Climate Science
- Soil Science
- Water Resources Management
- Biogeography
- Indigenous Knowledge System

- Urban and Regional Planning
- Transport Studies
- Demography
- Tourism Studies
- Geographic Information System (GIS)
- Disaster Risk Management

GUIDELINES FOR PAPER SUBMISSION

MANUSCRIPT PREPARATION

- Language: British English
- Format: Microsoft Word (MS)
- Paper Size: A4
- Font: Times New Roman
- Font Size: 12
- Line Spacing: Double
- Page Limit: 20 pages (excluding references)
- Abstract: Not more than 250 words, single-spaced
- Keywords: 4-5

MANUSCRIPT STRUCTURE

- Title
- Authors' names and affiliations (including emails of all authors, with the corresponding author clearly indicated)
- Abstract
- Introduction
- Methodology
- Findings
- Conclusion
- Recommendations

REFERENCES

- Format: APA
- Line Spacing: Single with hanging indent
- Space between references: 12 pt

SUBMISSION

- Submit to:
geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng
- Include evidence of payment of nonrefundable assessment fee of ₦10,000 (Ten thousand Naira only)

PUBLICATION FEE

Upon acceptance, submit the reviewed manuscript with evidence of payment of a non-refundable fee of ₦20,000 (Twenty thousand Naira only)

BANK DETAILS

- **Account Name:** GEOSTUDIES FORUM
- **Account Number:** 2324256060
- **Bank:** UBA

CONTENTS

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF OPEN SPACES AND THE LOCATION OF MECHANIC WORKSHOPS IN RESIDENTIAL AREAS OF AKURE TOWNSHIP <i>O. B. Akinbamijo, F. K. Omole, and M. K. Alakinde</i>	1 - 16
ANALYSIS OF THE SPATIAL PATTERN OF DIVORCE ACROSS THE SENATORIAL ZONES OF BENUE STATE, NIGERIA <i>Mary Otanwa Ubi, Andrew Egba Ubogu and Olanrewaju Yusuf Yahaya</i>	17 - 35
ANALYSIS OF FLOOD DISASTER RISK AND EXPOSURE IN THE COMMUNITIES OF KIRI DAM'S CATCHMENT, ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Ikusemoran Mayomi, Mukthar Alhaji, and Sambo Rita</i>	36 - 54
USE OF MOTORCYCLE AS ALTERNATIVE MEANS OF TRANSPORT IN OGBOMOSO, NIGERIA <i>Saka Nurudeen, Raji Abdulquadri Akande, and Taiwo Luqman Adedeji</i>	55 - 68
EXAMINATION OF CO-OPERATORS' SATISFACTION WITH STRATEGIES OF HOUSING FINANCE OF COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN KWARA STATE <i>Abdullahi Taiye Ibrahim, Sakariyau, Jamiu Kayode, Ajibade, Kayode Rasheed, AbdulHafeez, and Sulaiman AbdulKarim</i>	69 - 83
EVALUATION OF LAND USE LAND COVER CHANGES OF KIMBA/RITAWA GRAZING RESERVE IN NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA <i>Abubakar Hassan</i>	84 - 90
LAND SUITABILITY ASSESSMENT FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT USING GIS AND MULTI-CRITERIA EVALUATION APPROACH IN KATSINA METROPOLIS, KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Yahaya Zayyana Ibrahim and Safiyanu Mohammed</i>	91 - 100
TOWARDS URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY: MANAGEMENT AND CHALLENGES OF ELECTRONIC WASTE IN MAIDUGURI METROPOLIS, BORNO STATE <i>Kodiya M. A., Abdussalam B., Yusuf F. I., Buba W., and Yusuf A.</i>	101 - 116

EDITORIAL BOARD

- Dr I.O Orire:** orire.io@unilorin.edu.ng
08032942992
- Prof. L.T. Ajibade:** edabijalt@unilprin.edu.ng
08075251963
- Dr B.A. Usman:** usman.ba@unilorin.edu.ng
08036909201
- Dr Toluwalope M. Agaja:** agaja.tm@unilorin.edu.ng
07032329906
- Prof. Roda M. Olanrewaju:** lamoji@unilorin.edu.ng
08057674931
- Prof. Afolabi M. Tunde:** afolabi@unilorin.edu.ng
08038540145

EDITORIAL ADVISORY BOARD

- Prof. Gbadegesin, A. S. -** Dept. of Geography, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.
08033661346
adeniyig55@gmail.com
- Prof. Abdullahi, John -** Dept of Geography, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.
08036821438
drajohn74@gmail.com
- Prof. Ogunbodede, E. Funlayo -** Dept. of Geography & Planning Sciences, Adekunle Ajasin
University, Akungba, Ondo State.
08077860313
emmanuel.ogunbodede@aaua.edu.ng
- Prof. Akoteyon, I. S. -** Dept. of Environmental Management, Lagos State University,
Ojo, Lagos State. 08023161616
isaiah.akoteyon@lasu.edu

PATRON

- Prof. Adedayo, A. F. (Rtd.) -** Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of
Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

JOURNAL'S CONTACTS

Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

Emails: geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng, edabijalt@unilorin.edu.ng

Website: Visit the journal website at: Geo-Studies Forum

ANALYSIS OF THE SPATIAL PATTERN OF DIVORCE ACROSS THE SENATORIAL ZONES OF BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

Mary Otanwa Ubi, Andrew Egba Ubogu, Olanrewaju Yusuf Yahaya

Department of Geography, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, 5001, Nigeria

Corresponding author, Email address: otanwamary@gmail.com

Abstract: *The study examined the spatial pattern of divorce across the three senatorial zones and the Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Benue State from the period 2009-2022. Data on the causes of divorce was obtained from respondents from all the Area Courts in the Twenty-Three LGAs of Benue State in order to achieve the aim of this study. The findings revealed that the total divorce cases recorded across the senatorial zones for the period under study was 6731 and the mean is 2243.6. Benue South Senatorial Zone (Zone C) records of divorce cases were observed to be the highest in Benue State. Financial Stress, religious reasons, modernization/urbanization among others were reasons advanced for the high incidences of divorce recorded in this zone. At the level of LGAs, it was observed that Otukpo (>58.73), Makurdi (between 44.08 - 53.73) and Ogbadibo (between 29.41- 44.07) recorded the highest divorce cases while Guma, Gwer-West, Gwer-East, Konshisha, Vandiekya, Katsina-Ala, Ukum, Logo, Tarka, Guma, Buruku, Obi and Ohimini LGAs recorded the least cases of divorce. Also, the average divorce rate for the LGAs in Benue State was 292.6. The study therefore recommended implementation of divorce preventive measures, such as premarital counselling and early intervention programs in areas characterized by high divorce to help address marital issues before they escalate and to also reduce the high incidences of divorce in the study area.*

Keywords: Divorce, marriage, spatial, pattern, senatorial zone

INTRODUCTION

Prior to the 20th century, marriage was seen as sacred and when made legal in a recognized institution was treated as a covenant and strictly adhered to (Eze, 2009). Therefore, the rate at which couples divorced was ignorable. Unfortunately, upholding marital vows are apparently becoming unrealistic in the 21st century as this is evident in the overwhelming increase in the number of single parent households, which has several effects on the offspring (Wajim, 2020). According to scholarly researches conducted in sub-Saharan Africa, among the causes of the region's increased divorce and separation rates are modernization, urbanization, matrilineal

descent, early marriage, and infertility (Takyi, 2001).

According to Bongaarts, Frank, and Lesthaeghe (1984), divorce was the main reason for marriage breakup in sub-Saharan Africa. The study observed that the number of first marriages that ended in divorce were 7% for those married within the period of (0-4 years) to about 20% for those that lasted for 30 years and above. In the majority of the world's nations, the family's structure and organization have undergone substantial changes. Increase in the number of couples choosing divorce and legal separation as substitutes to troubled

marriage stands out among the various changes. For instance, based on all marriages

consummated within the period of fifty years (1964 to 2019) in England and Wales, the average total divorce rate was 31.8% (Divorce statistics, United Kingdom, 2018). A divorce occurred in 35.3% of marriages lasting 50 years, 42% of marriages lasting 40 years, 43.6% of marriages lasting 30 years, 36% of marriages lasting 20 years, and 18.9% of marriages lasting 10 years. The divorce rate in the United Kingdom is believed to be 42%.

Bongaarts, Frank, and Lesthaeghe (1984) noted that divorce is majorly responsible for marital disintegration in sub-Saharan Africa. These substitutes to marriage that were previously perceived to be a Western lifestyle, are progressively becoming mainstream in sub-Saharan African countries. It was discovered that the percentage of first marriages that ended in divorce ranged from 7% for the shortest marriages (0-4 years) to nearly 20% for the oldest (30 years and over). Recent researches revealed a rising tendency of marriage dissolution through divorce and separation in sub-Saharan Africa. According to Takyi (2001), divorce disrupts 35% of women's marriages in Ghana, 38% of women's marriages in Togo, and 29% of women's marriages in Mauritania after 30 years of marriage. The 2010 Ghana population and housing census revealed that divorce and separation prevalence for those who had ever been married were 58.6 and 32.2 per 1000, respectively (Ghana Statistical Service, 2010). No ethnic group has been found to be in favor of divorce in Ghana, where it is detested and considered as a sign of culture decay. Despite this, there are a lot of divorce cases in Ghana. Six hundred and

eighteen (618) customary marriages were dissolved compared to one thousand five hundred and eleven (1,511) marriages registered, according to an online publication (Public Agenda, 2008).

According to the Nation Magazine (2010), divorce rates are rising in Kenya and might be even higher if it weren't for the exorbitant expense of divorce. Despite the fact that the number of divorce cases filed in court has significantly increased, many couples still choose to seek legal counsel and resolve their divorce outside of court because of the high costs of doing so. In addition to the exorbitant legal fees, couples with irreconcilable disagreements are frequently deterred from going to court for private reasons, religious considerations, familial pressure, or even mutual consent. However, most recent figures show a continuous increase in divorce cases. Divorce cases were at least 101, 115, 206, 296 and 295 in each of the years 2001 through 2005, but increased to 357 and 369 in each of the years 2007 and 2008 (Nation Magazine 2010).

Although the incidence of divorce and separation in Nigeria is not thoroughly recorded, previous studies have shown that high divorce rates have been a component of the country's nuptiality culture in many regions (Solivetti, 1994). The high rate of remarriage and stigma surrounding divorce, however, mask the true occurrence. Solivetti (1994) found that divorce rate per 1000 population in 1979 ranged from 11.0 to 19.9; higher than the prevailing rates in some European countries at the time. This information was obtained from the divorce cases reported by local courts and demographic field work in the Niger valley of Sokoto State in northern Nigeria. In 2016, official statistics suggested that the dissolution of marriage in Nigeria was uncommon. According to the National Bureau of statistics,

just 0.2% of men and 0.3% of women had legally dissolved their marriage. However, there is no doubt that the above statistical data is inapplicable in the present times. According to Vanguard Newspaper (2020), separation rates in Nigeria recorded 14% increase, the present statistics mirror a rather negative trend.

According to Ochogwu (2021), the situation is similar in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), where more than 4,000 couples filed for divorce in less than two months (between January and February, 2020), with some of the marriages being less than a year old. Ochogwu, (2021) observed that the figure is higher in the Alkali and sharia customary courts located within the Federal Capital Territory. Additionally, Kano State alone had over one million divorcees (Yakubu 2019). These numbers demonstrate that the divorce rate is highly frightening and rising. In the same vein, Otanwa (2017) noted that there is a growing divorce rate in Makurdi LGA of Benue State. About 35 marriages ended in divorce in 2017, 50 divorces in 2018, 44 in 2019, 26 in 2020, and 52 in 2021 as recorded in the area courts situated in the study area. These statistics are

not complete enough because divorces that occurred outside of the legal system are not registered, despite the fact that this appears to be a widespread practice among the locals.

Although, several studies have been conducted on divorce globally, especially in Nigeria and Benue State in particular, the dearth of scholarly research on the spatial pattern of divorce taking into account the three senatorial zones that serve as the geopolitical divisions of Benue State constitutes the main crux of this study.

Description of the Study Area

Benue State lies within the lower river Benue trough in the middle belt region of Nigeria. Its geographic coordinates are Longitude $7^{\circ} 30' 0''$ E to $9^{\circ} 50' 0''$ E and latitude $6^{\circ} 20' 0''$ N to $8^{\circ} 20' 0''$ N. It shares boundaries with five other states namely: Nassarwa State to the north, Taraba State to the east, Cross-River State to the south, Enugu State to the south-west and Kogi State to the west. The Benue State also shares a common boundary with the Republic of Cameroon on the south-east (Mtonga, 2000). Figure 1 shows the map of the study area.

Figure 1: The study Area

Source: Adapted from the Benue State Ministry of Lands, Survey and Solid Minerals, 2011.

The population of Benue State, one of Nigeria's middle belt states, was estimated at 4,253,641 in the 2006 census, and projected to be 7,147,590 in 2023 with a growth rate of 3.05%. Its population density is 99 people per km², with a land area of 34,059 km². The major tribes in Benue State includes; Tiv, Idoma, Igede while Etulo, Jukun, and Abakwa are minority tribes having very low population.

Agriculture is the main source of employment in Benue State, employing over 70% of the working population. As a result, Benue is currently the country's leading food producer. Since 98% of Nigerians do not already use the most of the new tactics, it can yet be improved. In terms of mechanization, plantation agriculture and agroforestry are still in their infancy. The use of agricultural inputs such as pesticides, fertilizers, better seeds, and other foreign methods is increasing. However, issues with availability and

cost still exists. The crops cultivated in the research region include soy beans, groundnuts, beniseed, palm oil, rice, peanuts, citrus fruits, yam, cassava, sweet potatoes, beans, maize, millet, guinea corn, and vegetables. Based on data from Statista (2019). The poverty rate in Benue State is 32.9%. Poverty in Benue is extreme, widespread, and complex; it has increased over the last few decades and is particularly noticeable in rural regions. Only about one-third of people have access to health facilities, and only 5% of patients from remote areas can visit community health centers. Declining soil fertility, soil erosion, bushfires, floods, deforestation, pollution, inadequate waste management, disregard for the agricultural sector, and a lack of infrastructure that impedes the state's socioeconomic and agricultural development are major environmental issues in the state that affect the rural poor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopted both the quantitative and qualitative approaches to data collection to collect data for this research. The qualitative data involved a focus group discussion with the divorcees and in-depth interview. In each of the three selected LGAs, two (2) FGDs were conducted, one for males only and the other for females only, making it six (6) FGDs in all. Given that the subject being discussed is so delicate, separating the men and women will help prevent disputes. Furthermore, talking to others of the same gender will calm them and allow them to express themselves freely. The FGD participants were five (5) in number; the choice of this number will help to break any tie in their responses if the need arises and the sizable number will be easy to manage during the exercise. More so, the peculiarity of study and the area made it difficult for the researcher to gather more participants as many were not comfortable disclosing some information to the

researcher who is a stranger to them, this was observed during the reconnaissance survey. In-depth interviews (IDIs) with informants such as, judges of area courts, court registrars, clergy, community leaders and marriage counselors were also conducted in each of the selected Local Government Areas to gather detailed information on divorce in the study area, in all 15 (Fifteen) of them were interviewed.

Also, information on the factors responsible for divorce in the study area were acquired from respondents using a structured questionnaire. There are three senatorial districts and twenty three (23) LGAs that make up the study area. The study picked one Local Government from each of the senatorial districts. The Local Government chosen is the most urbanized in each of the senatorial districts in Benue State. The reason for this choice is due to availability of data needed for this study. Secondly, the large and heterogeneous nature of the population in these selected LGAs will provide a good sample of the population without bias. As such, the following Local Government Areas were chosen; Kwande, Makurdi and Otukpo.

The target respondents are divorcees and those who were divorced but later remarried. Snowball and purposive sampling techniques were adopted to administer the questionnaire. The choice of these techniques is because only divorcees and those who were once divorced but have remarried may offer insight into the causes of divorce. The projected population of the selected LGAs in the study area is 1,399, 274. Yamane, (1961) sample size determination formula was used to obtain sample size of 400. The wards from each of the selected LGA were chosen using purposive sampling technique in order to pin point areas where divorce is high as noted during reconnaissance survey. The 400 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents in the wards till they got exhausted.

The responses from the questionnaire administered to the respondents on the causes of divorce were analyzed using percentages. Also, records of divorce cases were obtained from Area Courts in all the twenty-three (23) Local Government Areas in Benue State for the period 2009-2022. The spatial pattern of divorce across the senatorial zones of the study area was analyzed from the divorce records obtained from these courts in the study area and shown on maps drawn with the aid of GIS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

THE CAUSES OF DIVORCE

Twelve factors were outlined as the causes of divorce and expressed as percentages as seen in Figure 2. The major causes of divorce in the study area as indicated by the respondents to be adultery with 10%, followed by Nagging and wife battering, inability to satisfy spouse sexually, inability to meet the financial and moral needs of the family and in-laws interference with 9% each. Women's economic independence, short courtship before marriage, failure to have children, absence of male children and level of educational attainment with 8% each. The least causes of divorce as revealed by Figure 2 are poverty and age difference between the couple with 7%.

Figure 2: The Causes of Divorce in Benue State

The simple fact is that every couple owes his/her partner fidelity and faithfulness in their union, this makes many couples see any act of infidelity as a breach of their marital vows and may decide to quit the marriage if his/her spouse is unfaithful. This finding is in agreement with that of Jekayinfa

(2010) and Otanwa (2017) who both opined that having other sexual relationships in marriage leads to divorce. The least causes of divorce as revealed by this study are poverty and age difference between couples (8%). This finding is in contrast with that of Karney and

Bradbury (2005) who argued that financial strain is a significant predictor of marital distress and divorce, as couples facing poverty are more likely to experience conflicts that lead to the dissolution of marriage. The reason for the disparity in this finding may be due to the locations where these studies were conducted, while this study was conducted in Nigeria, the study by Karney and Bradbury (2005) was conducted in the USA. These two locations have variations in their culture, norms, religious beliefs, behavior and how they perceive marriage. The finding by this study that age difference between couples is among the least causes of divorce also contradicts the findings made by Wolfinger (2017) who in a study found out that couples with a significant age difference are more likely to divorce compared to couples with a smaller age gap. The disparity in this study could also be as result of the climates where these studies were conducted.

THE SPATIAL PATTERN OF DIVORCE ACROSS THE SENATORIAL ZONES OF BENUE STATE

The spatial pattern of divorce across the senatorial zones in Benue State was revealed in Figure 3. Benue State, the study area is divided into three (3) senatorial zones; Zone A (Benue North East Senatorial Zone), Zone B (Benue North West Senatorial Zone and Zone C (Benue South Senatorial Zone). Zone A is made up of Katsinala, Konshisha, Kwande, Logo, Ukum, Ushongo and Vandeikya LGAs. Zone B is consisting of Buruku, Gboko, Guma, Gwer East, Gwer West, Makurdi and Tarka LGAs while Zone C consists of Otukpo, Ado, Agatu, Apa, Obi, Ogabdibo, Oju, Ohimini and Okpokwu LGAs.

The study revealed that Zone C recorded 3871 cases of divorce thereby making it the senatorial zone with the highest cases of divorce in Benue state followed by zone B with 1453 cases, and zone A with the least (1407) divorce cases recorded (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Number of divorce cases recorded in the Senatorial Zones from 2009-2022.
Source: Adapted from the Benue State Ministry of Lands, Survey and Solid Minerals, 2011.

Figure 4: Mean Divorce across the senatorial zones in Benue State.

Figure 4 presents the mean divorce for the senatorial zones in Benue State. Zone A recorded a total of 1407 divorce cases zone B recorded 1453 cases while Zone C recorded 3871 cases. The mean divorce rate recorded across the senatorial zones for the period under study is 2243.6. The mean divorce for Benue North East senatorial zone (Zone A) and Benue North West senatorial zone (Zone B) both fall below the mean divorce for the three senatorial zones hence, the reason their bars are fall below the mean line on the chart. Benue South senatorial zone on the other hand recorded 3871 divorce cases which is outrageously high when compared to the mean divorce of the three senatorial zones as seen in Figure 4.

The following reasons accounts for the low prevalence of divorce in the Benue North East senatorial zone (Zone A) and Benue North West senatorial zone (Zone B) of Benue State. These answers were obtained from the focus group discussion and in-depth interview conducted with stakeholders such as court registrars, judges, lawyers, community heads and the clergy. A participant of the IDI (In-depth-interview) that was held in one of the LGAs has this to say concerning the low prevalence of divorce recorded in Benue North East senatorial zone (Zone A) and Benue North West senatorial zone (Zone B);

Most of the people you find in these areas are exposed, financially stable and generally literate. Another factor is that we did not have area courts in some of the LGAs until recently. I believe we would have recorded more cases than we currently have now if the courts were established earlier. (IDI with Participant I, Makurdi, 2023).

A fair number of people from these zones (A and B) are financially stable when compared to those in zone C. Economic stability can alleviate stressors related to basic needs, such as food,

housing and healthcare which can positively impact the overall wellbeing of the relationship. The findings of the study by Sawhill and Venator (2014) is in agreement with this finding as the study asserted that financial stability can serve as foundation for maintaining marriages.

The two zones (A and B) are predominantly made up of the Tivs who are well exposed due to education, environment, media, and interactions with others. Exposure plays a significant role in handling conflicts by fostering understanding, tolerance and empathy which are essential in handling conflicts. The statement made by the IDI participant supports the finding made by Adebowale *et al.* (2013) where the researcher found out that there is a strong association between education levels and divorce rates in Nigeria as marriages were found to be more stable with the educated couples.

The absence/late establishment of area courts in some LGAs like Buruku, Tarka, Ukum and Gwer-west is also one of the reasons why fewer divorce cases were recorded in these zones as stated by one of the IDI participants. The absence of courts translates to no court sittings/hearings and no divorces granted or recorded.

On the other hand, the responses from the FGD participants held in Otukpo LGA revealed that the high incidence of divorce recorded in Zone C is attributed to financial stress, religion, and modernization/urbanization. Some participants in the FGD reported these;

My former husband could not fend for the family, we were always in need of the basic necessities. We were frustrated and had quarrels regularly so we parted ways eventually because he felt insulted

by me and i also felt neglected by his inability to provide for us. (FGD Participant IV, Otukpo LGA, 2023).

This FGD statement is in line with the finding by Dew and Dakin (2011) who in a study established that financial stress significantly increases the likelihood of divorce as it leads to constant worries about paying bills, making ends meet or dealing with debts.

Another IDI participant who is a community leader gave his response as follows;

Some Idomas are Muslims while others are Traditional worshippers, these religions permit divorce on certain grounds, hence the reason you find many divorcees in this community. Again the abandonment of the Alekwu tradition (the worship of a deity) by many people due to Christianity and modernization has made many marriages here prone to divorce (IDI Participant VI, 2023).

Again, this finding supports that of Okon (2011) who argued that religion, which is intended to be a stronghold of the society occasionally becomes an architect to the destruction of the society as change of denomination and teachings from some religious leaders can cause problems that will eventually lead to divorce. More so, Rezazadeh (2011) asserted that modernization process have led to changes in marital relationships and an increase in divorce rates. The inflow of people from various parts of the country to Otukpo has brought about interaction and assimilation of other cultures/habits that can trigger divorce. More so, the drift from traditional religion to Christianity led to the abandonment of the worship of *Alekwu* (a deity in Idoma land). The deity chastised married couples from committing adultery and other immoral acts in marriage as there are grave consequences for going against the deity, the situation has however taken a new turn as many people have shunned this practice and turned to Christianity which is more liberal.

Figure 5 shows a map of the study area on which the number of divorce cases recorded in all the 23 Local Governments Areas in Benue from 2009-2022 were plotted. A suitable scale was adopted to accommodate the total divorce cases for each of the LGAs as shown on Figure 5.

Figure 5: Number of Divorce Cases recorded according to Local Government Areas (2009-2022).
Source: Adapted from the Benue State Ministry of Lands, Survey and Solid Minerals, 2011.

Evident from Figure 5, Otukpo LGA has the highest number of divorce cases (above 822) recorded for the period under investigation and so for easy identification, red colour was used to depict it so that at a glance, one could easily notice it. The following reasons account for the high divorce cases recorded in Otukpo LGA as obtained during the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) conducted by the researcher in Otukpo LGA.

Before now, marriages were more stable with the Idomas because the people valued it and were cool

headed but now many men and women mingle with people from other tribes and adopt bad habits. Aside this, other reasons for the current increase in divorce here are poverty and religion (FGD, Otukpo, 2023).

Over the years Otukpo LGA has grown from a small to a big town due to it serving as the traditional headquarters of all the Idomas, the presence of the seat of the Ochi'Idoma (The head of the Idoma area traditional council), presence of higher institutions of learning, its

strategic location makes it a gate way between the northern and southern parts of the country, infrastructural development among others have made a lot of people from far and near come to settle down in Otukpo LGA. This inflow of people from various parts of the country has brought about interaction and assimilation of other cultures/habits that can trigger divorce. This finding agrees with that of (Mahadevan (2020) who opined that westernization/urbanization of cities triggers divorce. Otukpo LGA despite being urbanized still lacks well paid jobs and industries thereby causing poverty among the people. Lack of basic necessities subjects a union to strain thereby weakening the bound that the couple has. Prolong strains eventually splits the couple. This finding agrees with the submission of an internet article titled, "Top Reasons for Divorce (2014)" which suggested that one of the main causes of divorce could be a husband's unemployment which translates into financial difficulties and can put a married couple under a lot of stress leading to frequent arguments and poor communication.

Majority of Idomas are practicing Catholics, the Catholic Church annuls marriages contracted under deceit if it is proven that one or both parties entered into the marriage under false pretenses or with a significant deception that undermines the validity of the marriage. This gives room for marriages contracted in the church to be made void. It is however important to note that very few marriages are annulled as the church must be convinced beyond reasonable doubts before annulling any union. This finding is in line with that of Okon, (2011) who asserted that religion, which is intended to be a stronghold of the society occasionally becomes an architect to the destruction of the society as this is apparent from the role religion plays in causing divorce.

It is also apparent from Figure 5 that there are LGAs with less than 207 cases of divorce thereby making them the LGAs with the least cases of divorce. For easy identification, they are depicted with blue colour. They include; Guma, Gwer-West, Gwer-East, Konshisha, Vandiekya, Katsina-Ala, Ukum, Logo, Tarka, Guma, Buruku, Obi and Ohimini LGAs. The following reasons are advanced for the less cases of divorce recorded in these areas as stated by the participants of the FGD and In-depth interviews

- i. **Absence of Courts:** The absence of area courts in some of these locations for so many years have made it impossible for them to handle divorce cases let alone keep such records. This has led to few cases of divorce been recorded in these locations.
- ii. **Enlightenment:** Enlightenment is one of the reasons why divorce is low in some of the LGAs. Generally, enlightened people seek for help when faced with issues instead of taking hasty decisions and this is equally applied when issues arise in their marriages rather than resorting to divorce. This finding supports the assertion made by Finnegan and McNulty (2013) that enlightenment brings about conflict resolution and marital satisfaction resulting to healthier relationships.
- iii. **Poor Record Keeping:** Due to the underdevelopment of some of these locations, records are poorly kept. Some of the books where these records are kept have been destroyed by termites, some have been misplaced while some were not updated as and when due thereby leading to loss of data.
- iv. **Religion:** Christianity (Catholics) dominate these areas where low cases of divorce were recorded. Christianity frowns at divorce hence the reason for the low divorces in these areas as efforts are made to resolve marital issues except in the case of deceit. This result is consistent with the findings of Barna Group (2008) who observed that among the population segments with the lowest likelihood of having been divorced are Catholics with 28%.

For a broader understanding of the problem under investigation, the mean divorce rate in the study area was also taken into consideration. The mean divorce rate for Benue State is 292.6. Thus the LGAs whose divorce rates are less than 292.6 have low incidences of divorce while those whose divorce rates are higher than 292.6 have high incidences of divorce. A suitable scale was chosen to accommodate all the classes of the mean (<14.75->58.73). The LGAs with small dark green proportional circles are those whose divorce rates are less than 14.75. The LGAs

includes; Gwer-East, Gwer-West, Guma, Ohimini, Obi, Konshisha, Vandeikya, Katsina-Ala, Ukum, Logo, Tarka and Buruku. Closely followed to the ones depicted with dark green proportional circles are those with lemon green circles with their divorce rates ranging from 29.41- 44.07. These LGAs includes, Apa, Oju, Ado, Ushongo and Gboko. It is obvious from Figure 6 that Otukpo LGA has divorce rate greater than 58.73. For easy identification, Otukpo LGA is depicted with a large red proportional circle.

Figure 6: Mean divorce for the LGAs from 2009-2022.

Source: Adapted from the Benue State Ministry of Lands, Survey and Solid Minerals, 2011.

Similarly, the mean divorce rate in Benue State was plotted on a bar chart so as to easily identify the areas that have low and high cases of divorce

when compared to the mean divorce for the study area.

Figure 7: Mean Divorce in Benue State

The Mean divorce rate for the study area was calculated and the value is 292.6. To identify the areas with high or low divorce cases, a bar graph was drawn as seen in fig 7. The LGAs with high divorce rates includes; Agatu, Kwande, Makurdi, Ogbadibo, Okpokwu and Otukpo as their rates are higher than the mean divorce for Benue State which is 292.6. All the LGAs with high divorces listed above are urban/semi urban areas with a heterogeneous population. From previous researches such as that of Onyeneho and Ojukwu (2010) and Nwadinigwe (2017), it has been established that there is a strong link between urbanization and prevalence of divorce due to change in social norms and values, economic pressures, changing gender roles, and access to legal and social support services in urban centres.

Those with low divorce rates (below 292.6) are Ado, Apa, Buruku, Gboko, Guma, Gwer-West, Gwer-East, Katsina-Ala, Konshisha, Logo, Obi, Ohimini, Oju, Tarka, Ukum, Ushongo and Vandeikya LGAs as seen in Figure 7. The LGAs with low divorce rates as observed in Figure 7 are mostly from the Benue North East senatorial zone (Zone A) and Benue North West

senatorial zone (Zone B) of Benue State (Buruku, Gboko, Guma, Gwer-West, Gwer-East, Katsina-Ala, Konshisha, Logo, Tarka, Ukum, Ushongo and Vandeikya). During the IDI conducted, the reasons for the low divorce recorded in these areas were noted to include strong family ties, respect for cultural values and norms, in these LGAs. Here is the statement made by the community head.

Our people are known for upholding traditional values that prioritizes marriages as many families try their best to act as mediators to their children’s troubled marriages in order to avert shame and disgrace to their families. This practice has greatly helped marriages to thrive in our communities (IDI, Katsina-Ala LGA , 2023).

This finding is in line with that of Folayan (2009) who asserted that cultural norms and practices influences marital stability, particularly through kinship systems and communal support.as it brings about encouragement, empathy and reassurance

which helps couples navigate conflicts and emotional distress more effectively.

Also, low divorce rates were observed from Ado, Apa, Ohimini, Obi and Oju LGAs which fall under the Benue South Senatorial District (Zone C). The statement below explains the low divorce rates recorded in some of the LGAs in the Benue South Senatorial District (Zone C).

I can only account for the number of divorces we have handled here from the time i assumed duty, this is because the books where these records were kept were not handed to me. More so, we handle very few cases of divorce here because many of the people here do not understand why they should spend money going to the court to get divorced when they can just part ways (IDI, Obi LGA, 2023).

Poor record keeping by the courts and the practice of out of court settlement among couples may have also contributed to the low divorce records as observed in these LGAs.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study examined the spatial pattern of divorce across the senatorial zones of Benue State. The study investigated the causes of divorce and found out that adultery, nagging, wife battering and inability to satisfy spouse sexually are the major factors influencing divorce in the study area. The study also found out that among the three Senatorial zones in the study area, Zone C has the highest cases of divorce followed by Zone B while Zone A has the least cases. The study further obtained the

mean divorce across the senatorial zones of Benue State with Zone C's mean divorce being the highest (Higher than the mean Divorce for Benue state) while the means for Zone A and B is lower than the mean divorce of the study area. The study further revealed that Otukpo LGA recorded the highest cases of divorce of the 23 LGAs as well as mean divorce in Benue State, while Tarka LGA recorded the least divorce cases and mean in Benue State. The research exposed the major causes of divorce, the areas that are divorce prone, and also made recommendations which can help to curb divorce in the study area and the society at large.

The use of Geographic Information System (GIS) maps was employed to show the spatial pattern of divorce in the entire study area, divorce, clusters and anomalies that might not be apparent in raw data were made easy to identify by this study. This will guide the appropriate authorities to make policies and employ measures that will help curb divorce especially in the areas with high incidences of divorce.

The paper, therefore recommends that implementation of divorce preventive measures, such as premarital counseling and early intervention programs such as workshops, retreats and seminars in areas characterized by high divorce will help address issues before they escalate and also strengthen family bonds thereby reducing the prevalence of divorce in the study area.

REFERENCES

Adebowale, S. A., Fagbamigbe, F. A., Okareh, T. O., & Lawal, G. O. (2013). Education and Divorce in Nigeria. *Journal of Divorce and Remarriage*, 54(6), 481-502.

Barma Groups, (2008). New Marriage and Divorce Statistics Released. Retrieved from [https://www.google.com/search?q=Barma+Groups+\(March+2008\).+New+Marriage+an+Divorce+Statistics+Released.&og=&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBCDIwNTlqMGo3qAIIsAIB&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8](https://www.google.com/search?q=Barma+Groups+(March+2008).+New+Marriage+an+Divorce+Statistics+Released.&og=&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBCDIwNTlqMGo3qAIIsAIB&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8).

Benue State Ministry of Lands, Survey and Solid Minerals. (2011). Map of Benue State. Benue State Ministry of Lands, Survey and Solid Minerals. Retrieved from <https://www.iambenue.com/benue-state/benue-state-ministries/lands-and-survey/>.

Bongaarts, J., Frank, O. & Lesthaeghe, R. (1984). The Proximate Determinants of Fertility in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Population and Development Review*. 10(3), 511–537.

Dew, J., & Dakin, J. (2011). Financial Disagreements and Marital conflict tactics: The Mediating Role of Financial Management. *Journal of Financial Therapy*, 2(1), 23-41.

Divorce Statistics UK, (2022). Nimble Fins. Retrieved from [https://www.google.com/search?q=Divorce+Statistics+UK+\(2022\).+Nimble+fins&og=Divorce+Statistics+UK+\(2022\).+Nimble+fins&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIJCAEQIRgKKGKAB0gEIMTM4MGowajeoAgCwAgA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8](https://www.google.com/search?q=Divorce+Statistics+UK+(2022).+Nimble+fins&og=Divorce+Statistics+UK+(2022).+Nimble+fins&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIJCAEQIRgKKGKAB0gEIMTM4MGowajeoAgCwAgA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8)

Eze, E. (2009, June 20). Nigeria has Sufficient Laws to Protect Families. *Guardian Newspaper*, P. 9.

Finnegan, R. A., & McNulty, J. K. (2013). Approaching enlightenment: How Mindful Awareness and Compassion Predict Conflict Resolution and Marital Satisfaction. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 27(4), 540-549.

Folayan, O. (2009). Marital Stability among the Tiv of Central Nigeria: The Role of Cultural Norms and Practices. *Journal of Black Studies*, 39(6), 942-959.

Ghana Statistical Service. (2010). Population and Housing Census: National Analytical Report. Vol. 1. P 105.

Ghana Statistical Service. (2021). Population and Housing Census: National Analytical Report. Vol. 1. P 108.

Jekayinfa, A. A. (2010). Family Disorganization: A Case Study of the Causes and Consequences of Divorce in Kwara State. *Journal of Review of Studies in Social Science*, 2(1), 1-9.

Karnay, B. R., & Bradbury, T. N. (2005). Contextual Influences on Marriage: Implications for Policy and Intervention. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 14(4), 171-174.

Mahadevan, P. (2020). Western Culture Promotes divorce. Retrieved from <https://www.civilserviceindia.com/subject/Essay/western-culture-promotes-divorces2.html>

Mtonga, T., E. (2000). Market Gardening along the Flood Plain of River Benue in Makurdi Town: Unpublished B.Sc. Project, Department of Geography, Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria.

Nation Magazine (2010 April 7). Kenya divorce rate soars but high legal fees keeps in check.

Retrieve from [https://www.google.com/search?q=Nation+Magazine+\(2010+April\).+Kenya+divorce+rate+soars+but+high+legal+fees+keeps+in+check.&oq=Nation+Magazine+\(2010+April\).lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBCDEzMDJqMGo3qAIAsAIA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8#ip=1](https://www.google.com/search?q=Nation+Magazine+(2010+April).+Kenya+divorce+rate+soars+but+high+legal+fees+keeps+in+check.&oq=Nation+Magazine+(2010+April).lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBCDEzMDJqMGo3qAIAsAIA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8#ip=1)

Nwadinigwe, I. P. (2017). Patterns and Trends in Divorce and Remarriage in Southeastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 5(2), 123-137.

Nyagba, J. L, Kwanga, M.G. & Kerenku, A. T. (2000). Benue State: In: Nigeria, A people united, a Future Assured. A Survey of States. Vol 2. Millennium Edition.

Ochogwu, S. (2021 March 5). Alarming Rate of Divorce in Abuja, other states traced to the use of Kayan Mata. *Daily Post News*. Retrieved from <https://dailypost.ng/2021/03/05/alarming-rate-of-divorce-in-abuja-other-states-traced-to-use-of-kayan-mata/>

Okon, E. E. (2011). The Sociological Imagination of Religion. In O. E. Etim (Ed.), *Readings in the Scientific Study of Religion* Calabar: University of Calabar Press. pp. 224-246.

Onyeneho, S. N., & Ojukwu, J. C. (2010). Urbanization and the Dynamics of Marital Instability. *Global Journal of Applied, Management and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 56-68.

Otanwa, M. E. (2017). Assessment of the Trend and Effects of Divorce on Households in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, M. Sc. Dissertation submitted to the Department of Geography, Faculty of Earth and

Environmental Sciences. Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.

Rezazadeh, H. (2011). The Impact of Modernization on Marriage and Divorce in Iran: Application of Giddens' Theory. *Journal of Divorce and Remarriage*, 52(6), 441-450.

Sawhill, I., & Venator, J. (2014). Financial Stability as Foundation for Maintaining Marriages. *The Future of Children*, 24(2), 137-155.

Solivetti, L., M. (1994). Family, Marriage and Divorce in a Hausa Community: A Sociological Model. *Africa*. 64(2), 252–271.

Statista. (2019). Poverty Head Count Rate in Nigeria 2019 by State. Simona Varrella Publishers. Retrieved June 17, 2024, from <https://www.statista.com>.

Takyi, B., K. (2001). Marital Instability in an African Society: Exploring the Factors that influence Divorce Processes in Ghana. *Sociological Focus*. 34(1), 77–96.

Top Reasons for Divorce. (2014, June 26). Retrieved from <https://www.marriage.com/advice/divorce/10-most-common-reasons-for-divorce/>

Harbour Family Law, (2022). How Many Marriages end in Divorce in the UK? Retrieved from <https://www.harbourfamilylaw.co.uk/how-many-marriages-end-in-divorce-in-the-uk/#:~:text=Some%20of%20the%20current%20trends,of%204%25%20compared%20to%2019.>

Wajim, J. (2020). Single Parenting and its Effects on the Development of Children in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*, 7(4), 5891-5902.

Wolfinger, N. H. (2017). More Evidence that Age Difference between spouses can result in Divorce. *Family Studies*, 33(4), 385-401.

Yakubu, U. (2019 March 1). Deciphering the High Rate of Divorce. *Premium Times Newspaper*. p.18.

Yamane, T. (1961). *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis*, (3rded). New York, Harper and Row.